

Investigating the Sources of Dissatisfaction with ERP Systems

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Abstract- Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), is one of the latest technologies that many organizations have undertaken. Typically, ERP systems are software package composed of several modules, such as finance, human resources, sales, and production. It provides cross-organizational integration of data management throughout the business processes. Although there are many benefits of using the ERP systems, the potential users are not able to fully use the system. They are dissatisfied with the ERP system. The purpose of this research is to investigate the sources of dissatisfaction faced by the end-users of the ERP system. In order to approach this research, we have utilized a critical incident technique (CIT). The incidents are collected from 900 actual employees working in the Telecommunication company of Pakistan. The company has implemented the Oracle ERP systems from the last 10 years. For this study, we have only collected the data from the ERP module of accounts payable (AP), application implementation methodology (AIM) and accounts receivable (AR) module. The incidents are analyzed by using the vivo coding scheme. The results of this study conclude that most of the sources of dissatisfaction faced by employees on the AP module are related to technical failure

(119). While, on the AIM module, it is related to process failures (150). In the AR module, most dissatisfactions are related to both, technical failure (130) as well as the process failure (120).

Keywords: ERP system, Dissatisfaction, Critical incident technique (CIT), Human-computer interaction

I. INTRODUCTION

ERP stands for Enterprise Resource Planning. Other common names used are Enterprise Information Systems (EIS), Enterprise-Wide Systems (EWS) or Enterprise Systems (ES). ERP system can be defined as a single integrated and packaged information system that is used to integrate and manage the business flow within an enterprise [1]. The ERP system uses a single database to store various types of data throughout the entire organization. The ERP systems have significant benefits to offer for an enterprise in terms of operational efficiency [2]. The other reasons for adopting the ERP system is to speed up the operation process and reduced inventory so on. The ERP systems are used in a wide range of organizations such as health care, banks, and telecommunication sector. There are many modules in the ERP system such as finance, supply chain, human resource, customer relationship, and manufacturing, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: ERP modules[3]

There are many benefits of using the ERP systems. These benefits can be divided into five categories [4]:

- 1) operational
- 2) organizational
- 3) strategic
- 4) Managerial
- 5) IT infrastructure

TABLE I
BENEFITS OF ERP SYSTEMS

ERP Dimensions	Benefits of using ERP Systems
Operational	Decrease cost Customer services enhancement Faster transactions Reduce inventory Cycle time reduction
Organizational	Simplify professional knowledge Build common visions
Strategic	Support business growth Supports cost leadership Improve customer interaction Improve supplier's interaction
Managerial	Better management of resources More efficiently improve performance control

IT infrastructure	IT cost reduction Increased business flexibility
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Although there are many benefits of using the ERP systems, the existing literature is filled with many issues belong to the ERP system [5]. Some of the issues are related to ERP

implementation, while others are with respect to usability [6]. These issues are shown in the Table 2.

TABLE 2
ISSUES OF ERP SYSTEMS [7]

ERP Dimensions	Issues of using ERP Systems
Cost & Implementations	ERP implementation cost is very high. ERP software has poor functionality. It takes too much time to learn to use an ERP system. Difficult to use for occasional users. Error messages are not meaningful. Online help is not usable.
Usability	Difficult to find the required Information. Data entry can be very tedious. Users cannot see the current state of the system. It is difficult for users to find the next step when working in multiple document window.

II. DISSATISFACTION

There is not a standard definition of dissatisfaction. Some researcher takes the opposite factors of satisfaction to measure the dissatisfaction [8]. While others take it as two different concepts and think that satisfaction/dissatisfaction is affected by different sources. Some factors increase the

dissatisfaction if absent but do not increase satisfaction when present in the study. In this article, the dissatisfaction can be defined by any negative user experience with the ERP system [9]. There are three sources of dissatisfaction; internal, external, and situational as shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3
SOURCES OF DISSATISFACTION [10]

Sources of dissatisfaction	Description
<i>External Failure:</i>	
Technical failure	Technology is not working as calculated: slowness of application, bugs, and errors in the system.
Interaction	The complexity of application: challenging to use; no proper finalized, feelings of confusion.
Content	Content is not matching user needs: useless, Content is not fresh, misplaced, and flawed data.
Privacy	Privacy concerns: perceived insecurity
Process failure	Process failure: server down, speed of service, modification of an application

Internal Failure:

Consumer driven failure

Negative experiences caused by the user due to the human's action or mistakes

**Situational Failure:
Context**

Inability to function whenever and wherever: uncommon conditions, interference from the physical environment, other unfortunate situational events.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to approach this research, we have used the critical incident technique (CIT). The CIT is a set of procedures for collecting observations of behavior and then classifying them so that they are useful in addressing practical problems. In this technique, the respondents describe their single crucial positive or negative experiences with products and services [11]. The CIT is a content analysis technique, which uses self-reported stories, events, and phenomena. The purpose of the CIT technique is to understand the investigated phenomenon in detail. In CIT technique, the respondents are instructed to remember and describe the most dissatisfying experience in their own words [12]. We have chosen a critical incident technique because it is suitable according to the nature of our study. The reasons to choose CIT are as follow [13]:

- CIT comprises a straightforward qualitative method;
- CIT provides authentic, clear, and well-defined strategies for collection and analysis of data.
- CIT emphasizes on actual and true human involvements.
- CIT backs the development of useful implications.
- CIT is comparatively flexible; and

- CIT supports many other information science and education studies.

The research question to investigate for this study is as follow:

- RQ 1: What are the sources of dissatisfaction with the account payable module of the ERP system?
- RQ 2: What are the sources of dissatisfaction with the AIM module of the ERP system?
- RQ 3: What are the sources of dissatisfaction with the AR module of the ERP system?

IV. STUDY 1: ACCOUNT PAYABLE MODULE OF ERP SYSTEM

A. Data collection

We have collected the data from the 300 actual users working in the telecommunication company of Pakistan. This telecommunication company has implemented the Oracle ERP systems from the last 10 years. The data have been collected from the accounts payable module of ERP System. Out of 300, there are 210 male, and 90 respondents are female. The average age of the respondents are 28 years old. The demographic information of the respondents is as shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4
DEMOGRAPHIC DETAIL OF STUDY 1

Parameters	Description	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	210	70.0
	Female	90	30.0
Age	Less than 21 years	10	3.33
	21-29 years	220	73.33
	30-40 years	70	23.33

Experience with ERP system	0-24 months	40	13.33
	24-36 months	70	23.33
	>36 months	190	63.33

B. Data Analysis

The data have been analyzed by using content analysis method. In content analysis, we have used the vivo coding scheme. Three researchers participated in vivo coding scheme [14]. The first, two researchers read the negative incidents separately. They have coded the incident and check whether it is related to internal, external, or situational factors. After the code has been selected for internal or external factors, they are further classified into the subcategories. This process continued until the last incidents have been coded and subcategories. The authors of this paper have one of the coders of the incidents. The other coder is a master student who is independent of the full research process of this paper. After completing the coding, the researchers then met to compare coding and classifications. There are 270 agreements and 30 differences in coding among researchers. The agreement between the participants has been calculated as shown in Eq. (1) [15].

$$\frac{\Sigma(\text{agreements})}{\Sigma(\text{agreements}) + \Sigma(\text{differences})} = \frac{270}{270 + 30} = 0.9 \dots\dots (1)$$

There are 30 differences between the two researchers. To resolve the differences, a third independent researcher (another

Master student) are invited to read these 30 codes. He then has discussed the differences with the first two researchers. After the discussion, the differences are resolved with consensus. The consensus is developed based on the iterative process; reading the incidents, categorizing the incidents, rereading the incidents and recombine incidents until the consensus is reached. Most of the confusion are related to external factors and internal factors. Take an example, “scan paper is not open”. The first researcher referred this incident to external factor, but the second researcher referred this incident to internal factor. The third researcher joined the talk. After discussion and deep analysis, all three researchers agree that this incident is referred to external factor.

In this study, we have not found any incident related to situational failures because all the data is collected in the office environment. In the office environment, the situational factor, such as room temperature and poor light have not affected the working condition of the respondents. Some of the incidents from the Oracle Account Payable module with their relevant factors are shown in the Table 5.

TABLE 5
SAMPLE OF AP INCIDENTS

Factor	Sample incidents from accounts payable data
<i>External factors</i>	
Technical failure	“I was not able to print the invoices”
Process failure	“system required an update”
Interaction	“amount mismatch”, “feeling of confusing”
Privacy	“Invoices showing unapproved invoice”
Content	“flawed in invoices”
<i>Internal factors</i>	

Consumer-driven failure	“Payment to wrong vendor”
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C. Results

Most of the dissatisfaction with the Oracle account payable module is related to the external failure. There is a total of 261 external failures, as seen in Table 6. Among the external failure, the highest frequency value of failures is related to a subcategory of a technical failure (119). The other external

failures are process failures (67); interaction failures (53), privacy failures (15) and content failures 7. Internal failure has only one subcategory (consumer driven failure). There is a total of 39 failures in this category. The result of study 1 can be seen in the Table 6 as well as a pie chart.

TABLE 6
FREQUENCIES OF DISSATISFACTION

	Subcategories	Dissatisfying	
External	Technical failure	119	Total 261
	Process failure	67	
	Interaction	53	
	Privacy	15	
	Content	7	
Internal	Consumer driven failure	39	Total 39

Figure 2: Dissatisfying AP

V. STUDY 2: APPLICATION IMPLEMENTATION METHODOLOGY (AIM) MODULE OF THE ERP SYSTEM

A. Data Collection

For study 2, we have collected the 300 incidents from the same Telecommunication company in Pakistan. The data is collected on the Application implementation methodology (AIM) module of the ERP system. It is

collected during the time period from July 2018 to September 2018. Out of 300, 180 are male while 120 are female respondents. Their age ranges from 18 to 40 years. The experience of the respondents is from 0 to 3 years. The demographic information of the respondents is shown in the Table 7.

TABLE 7
DEMOGRAPHIC DETAIL OF AIM

Parameters	Description	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	180	60.0
	Female	120	40.0
Age	18- 21 years	40	13.33
	21-29 years	160	53.33
	30-40 years	100	33.33
Experience with ERP system	0-24 months	37	12.33
	24-36 months	74	24.66
	>36 months	189	63.00

B. Data Analysis

The data has been analyzed by using content analysis, and the total number of respondents are 300. For study 2, we have collected the incidents from Oracle Application implementation methodology (AIM) module of the ERP system. We adopted the same procedure as mention in study 1. There are 260 agreements and 40 differences in coding

among researchers. The agreement between the participants, calculated as shown in Eq. (2).

$$\frac{\Sigma(\text{agreements})}{\Sigma(\text{agreements}) + \Sigma(\text{differences})} = \frac{260}{260 + 40} = 0.87 \dots\dots (2)$$

Some of the sample incidents with their categories that have been analyzed by researcher 1 and 2 can be seen in the Table 8.

TABLE 8
SAMPLE INCIDENTS OF AIM

Factor	Sample incidents from AIM data
External factors	
Technical failure	“I am unable to view invoice in AIM pre-registration step due to error issue”
Process failure	“Update the bank account number of this invoice as it got rejected from the oracle due to "Supplier Bank Account attached to document payable is end dated”
Interaction	“Payment is cleared but unaccounted status”
Privacy	“Some of the accounts are restricted through Security Rules” Unapproved invoices
Content	“unlimited invoices”
Internal factors	
Consumer-driven failure	“Invoice has been registered to wrong vendor”, “pressed wrong button”

C. Results

Most of the dissatisfaction in the Oracle AIM module are related to external failure. A total of 265 external failures are recorded in the

AIM module, as seen in Table 9. Among the external failures, the highest frequency of failures is related to process failure (150). The other failure are technical failures (65),

interaction failures (32), privacy failures (7) and content failures 11. The Second type of failure is internal failure. A total of 35 internal

failures are recorded in AIM Oracle module. The result of study 2 can be seen in the Table 9 as well as a pie chart as shown in Figure 3.

TABLE 9
FREQUENCIES OF DISSATISFACTION

Subcategories		Dissatisfying	
External	Technical failure	65	Total 265
	Process failure	150	
	Interaction	32	
	Privacy	7	
	Content	11	
Internal	Consumer driven failure	35	Total 35

Figure 3: Dissatisfying AIM

VI. STUDY 3: ACCOUNT RECEIVABLE (AR) MODULE OF ERP SYSTEM

A. Data collection

For study 3, we have collected the 300 incidents from the same Telecommunication company in Pakistan. The data is collected on the Accounts receivable (AR) module of the

ERP system. It is collected during the time period from July 2018 to September 2018. Out of 300, 130 are male while 170 are female respondents. Their age ranges from 18 to 40 years. The experience of the respondents is from 0 to 3 years. The demographic information of the respondents is shown in the Table 10.

TABLE 10
DEMOGRAPHIC DETAIL OF AR

Parameters	Description	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	130	43.33
	Female	170	56.66
Age	18- 21 years	40	13.33
	21-29 years	160	53.33
	30-40 years	100	33.33
Experience with ERP system	0-24 months	37	12.33
	24-36 months	74	24.66
	>36 months	189	63.00

B. Data Analysis

The data have been analyzed by using content analysis, and the total number of respondents are 300. For study 3, we have collected the incidents from Oracle Accounts receivable (AR) module of the ERP system. We have adopted the same procedure as mention in study 1. There are 280 agreements and 20

differences in coding among researchers. The agreement between the participants, calculated as shown in Eq. (3).

$$\frac{\Sigma(\text{agreements})}{\Sigma(\text{agreements}) + \Sigma(\text{differences})} = \frac{280}{280 + 20} = 0.93 \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Some of the sample incidents with their categories that have been analyzed by researcher 1 and 2 can be seen in the Table 11.

TABLE 11
SAMPLE INCIDENTS OF AR

Factor	Sample incidents from AR data
<i>External factors</i>	
Technical failure	“I am not able to print the invoices”
Process failure	“Accounts receivable invoices upload issues”
Interaction	“interference line errors”
Privacy	“Unapproved invoices”
Content	“unlimited invoices”
<i>Internal factors</i>	
Consumer driven failure	“wrong template use”

C. Results

Most of the dissatisfaction in the Oracle AR module are related to external failure. A total of 282 external failures are recorded in the AR module, as seen in Table 12. Among the

external failures, the highest frequency of failures is related to technical failure (130) and process failure (120). The others failure are interaction failures (22), privacy failures (3) and content failures 7. The Second type of failure is the internal failure. A total of 18

internal failures are recorded in AR Oracle module. The result of study 3 can be seen in

the Table 12 as well as pie chart as shown in Figure 4.

TABLE 12
FREQUENCIES OF DISSATISFACTION

	Subcategories	Dissatisfying	
External	Technical failure	130	Total 282
	Process failure	120	
	Interaction	22	
	Privacy	3	
	Content	7	
Internal	Consumer driven failure	18	Total 18

Figure 4: dissatisfying AR

VII. COMPARISON OF THE STUDIES

In this section, we would like to compare the studies with respect to three research questions. The research questions are as follow:

RQ 1: What are the sources of dissatisfaction with the Account payable module of the ERP system?

In account payable module, most of the dissatisfaction are related to external failures. A total of 261 external failures are recorded. Among the external failure, the highest frequency value of failures is related to technical failure (119). The other external failures are process failures (67); interaction failures (53), privacy failures (15) and content failures (7). Internal failure has only one

subcategory (consumer driven failure). There is a total of 39 failures in this category.

RQ 2: What are the sources of dissatisfaction with the AIM module of ERP system?

In AIM module, most of the dissatisfaction are related to the external failures. A total of 265 external failures are recorded. Among the external failures, the highest frequency of failures is related to process failure (150). The others failure are technical failures (65), interaction failures (32), privacy failures (7) and content failures 11. The Second type of failure is the internal failure. A total of 35 internal failures are recorded in AIM Oracle module.

RQ 3: What are the sources of dissatisfaction with the AR module of ERP system?

Ans: In AR module of ERP system most of the dissatisfaction are related to the external failures. A total of 282 external failures are recorded in AR module. Among the external failures, the highest frequency of failures is related to technical failure (130) and process failure (120). The others failure are interaction failures (22), privacy failures (3) and content failures 7. The Second type of failure is the internal failure. A total of 18 internal failures are recorded in AR Oracle module. The comparison of study 1, 2 and 3 can be shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Comparison of study 1, 2 and 3

VIII. CONCLUSION

This study contributes to the knowledge of dissatisfaction with the ERP systems. The data sets include responses from both actual and potential users. It has been collected the data from the Telecommunication company in Pakistan by using critical incidents technique. The data has been collected from the Account payable, AIM, and AR module. The result of this study reveals that most of the dissatisfaction in the ERP system is generated by external and internal factors. Technical failure, process failure, and interaction are the most frequently reported sources. Finally, this study is conducted using data from three (AP, AIM) modules of ERP systems. Future studies should be conducted with other modules of ERP systems to verify the findings of this research.

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